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Three bypass diodes architecture at the limit

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Abstract

In this work we demonstrate that inhomogeneous illumination of state-of-the-art solar modules with three bypass diodes results in hot cells with critical peak temperatures of 164 °C. We examine two solar modules in the hot spot endurance test, one with 367.3 W_P featuring 72 full cells and the other with 388.6 W_P featuring 144 half cells. For the module with 72 cells we measure a maximum temperature of 164 °C, which results in a degradation of the encapsulation material and increases the risk of module failure. Our experiments show that the half cell module is advantageous in the hot spot endurance test compared to the full cell module. Although the half cell module has a higher power output than the full cell module we measure a cooler peak temperature of 150 °C. We also show that under certain shading conditions, the half cell module exhibits similar temperatures as the full cell module. Based on our experimental results we develop an electrical and a thermal model to predict the temperature of future solar modules in the hot spot endurance test. In our prediction we consider the trends of further increasing cell and module efficiencies, larger wafer formats, and larger solar modules. For the worst case we simulate a peak temperature of 176 °C at the module's surface, which significantly increases the risk of module failure. Our results show that future modules employing bifacial solar cells that are made from larger wafer formats, need a new protection against overheating. Three bypass diodes per module are no longer sufficient.

hot spot, solar module reliability, breakdown characteristics

1 Introduction

Current mismatch due to cell cracks or inhomogeneous illumination of solar panels may result in reverse biasing of solar cells within a photovoltaic (PV) module. Instead of generating, the reverse biased cells dissipate power and generate heat, which is also known as hot spot effect [1]. A hot spot can irreversibly damage the cell and module [2–5]. In general, state-of-the-art solar modules employ three bypass diodes as a protection against overheating. The diodes limit the reverse voltage of an inhomogeneously illuminated cell in the PV module and thus, mitigate the risk of hot spot failure [6]. Further, each solar module has to pass the hot spot endurance test according to the IEC 61215-2 MQT 09 standard for the certification [7]. Nevertheless, today this degradation effect is one of the most frequent failure mechanisms in modern PV systems [8–10]. Especially multi crystalline silicon (mc-Si) solar cells are prone to hot spots due to the local junction breakdown [11, 12]. Hence, many studies have investigated this effect for mc-Si solar cells and developed electrical and thermal models to simulate the effects of inhomogeneous illumination on PV panel [13–18].

However, today more than 60 % of the solar cells employ monocrystalline silicon (c-Si) solar cells [19]. Kim *et al.* showed, that c-Si solar cells may exhibit a homogeneously distributed breakdown behavior resulting in an evenly distributed heat generation in the cell and resulting in temperatures well below 100 °C [20]. Thus, these cells are less prone to local hot spot failure. Kim *et al.* also showed, that in case of 24 cells per string a significant amount of power is dissipated in a partially shaded cell, which may damage the module component. Nevertheless, the study shows no experimental results with modules exceeding critical temperatures or thermal modelling. Qian *et al.* compared half and full cell modules in theoretical and experimental studies [21, 22]. They also showed that half cell modules are beneficial in terms partial shading,

since they exhibit lower temperatures during hot spot experiments. The authors also reported on a phenomenon that during the experiment, cells in the non-shaded string became hot due to reverse biasing, though their work misses worst case experiments and they examine only a single string with 16 full cells and 32 half cells, which is less than for state-of-the-art modules with 20, 24 or more cells per bypass diode.

Moreover, advances in the recent years improved the cell and module efficiency, with passivated emitter and rear cells (PERC) becoming the new standard in terms of mass production and resulting in high efficiency modules exceeding module powers above 350 W_P [19, 23]. This development will also increase the dissipated power of reverse biased cells and brings the concept of three bypass diodes per module to the limit. The most critical developments that further exacerbate the hot spot issues are: i) The continuously improving cell and module efficiencies [19, 24]. ii) Larger wafer formats that are pushing into the market since they potentially reduce the production cost [19, 23, 25]. This also increases the area and the current of the solar cells, which increases the dissipated power at reverse bias. iii) The trend of bifacial modules, which also increases the cell current and results in various inhomogeneous illumination cases for solar modules [26]. iv) The increasing number of cells per module, which consequently increases the number of cells per bypass diode.

In this work we investigate two state-of-the-art full-sized modules and show that already today the three bypass diodes interconnection in half cell modules can result in module temperatures above 150°C . We investigate the breakdown characteristics of state-of-the-art PERC, that show a homogeneous breakdown characteristic and result in a uniform heating of the cell. Thus, we will denote these cells as hot cells in the following. Based on our cell and module measurements we develop an electrical and a thermal model to predict the cell and module temperatures for future solar modules employing three bypass diodes. We further employ the electrical model to elucidate the effect of reverse biasing of only marginally shaded cells in half cell modules.

2 Methodology

2.1 Measuring the cell parameters for the electrical model

We measure the illuminated, dark, and I_{SC} - V_{OC} current-voltage ($I(V)$) characteristics of 100 bifacial industrial c-Si PERC employing a LOANA measurement system [27]. Each PERC cell has an area of $156.75 \text{ mm} \times 156.75 \text{ mm}$ and features five busbars at the front and rear side. We model the $I(V)$ data with the double diode model using SCAN [28]. Furthermore, we measure the reverse $I(V)$ characteristics of 6 PERC with a Neonsee Solar Cell Analysis Systems [29]. This system allows for $I(V)$ measurements down to -40 V with a current limit of -15 A . The brass chuck for the rear contact maintains the 25°C during the measurement and also allows measurements at elevated temperatures. We measure the reverse $I(V)$ characteristics and the reverse biased electroluminescence image of one cell for a varying temperature T of (25, 35, ..., and 75) $^\circ\text{C}$ to determine the temperature coefficient for the breakdown voltage.

2.2 Measuring of the module characteristics

We examine two modules with PERC cells that are similar to the cells we measure in section 2.1. Each PERC features 5 cell interconnection ribbons on the front and rear side for the series interconnection of the cells. The cell to cell and the string to string spacing in each module is 3 mm.

Figure 1 (a) shows a sketch module M72 featuring 72 full PERCs with $158.75 \text{ mm} \times 158.75 \text{ mm}$. The module consists of 6 strings, each string containing 12 cells in a series connection. The three red colored diodes at the top of the module indicate the three bypass diodes, each in a split-junction box on the module's rear side. On the front and rear side the module employs a 3 mm thick glass. The red labels in Figure 1 (a) indicate the cells we test in the hot spot endurance test. For all measurements we attach a black foil to the rear side to avoid measurements artifacts due to the bifacial properties of the module.

Figure 1 (b) shows a sketch of module M144 featuring 144 half PERCs with $158.75 \text{ mm} \times 79.38 \text{ mm}$. The cells are equal to the cells in module M72 but cut into half cells to reduce the module's

Figure 1: Schematic of the examined modules with (a) showing module M72 and b) showing module M144.

series resistance losses [30]. The red labels in Figure 1 (b) indicate the cells we test in the hot spot endurance test and the white labels denote the cell numbering. The module consists of two submodules in a parallel connection, with the top submodule M144-T holding all cells from 1 through 72 and bottom submodule M144-B holding all cells from 73 through 144. The red colored diodes in the center indicate the split junction boxes with the bypass diodes. Each bypass diode is connected anti-parallel to a double string of submodule M144-T and M144-B. In contrast to M72 this module features a 3 mm thick front glass and a white colored polymer backsheets.

We measure the illuminated $I(V)$ characteristics of the modules with a HALM flasher system under standard testing conditions. Table 1 lists the modules' power output at the maximum power point (MPP) P_{MPP} , short circuit current I_{SC} , open circuit voltage V_{OC} as well as the current I_{MPP} and voltage V_{MPP} at MPP. We also measure the $I(V)$ characteristics for an irradiance of 800 W m^{-2} and 600 W m^{-2} to determine the modules' series resistance R_{S} [31].

Table 1: $I(V)$ data of module M72 and M144.

Module name	P_{MPP} [W]	I_{SC} [A]	V_{OC} [V]	I_{MPP} [A]	V_{MPP} [V]	R_{S} [$\Omega \text{ cm}^2$]
M72	367.3	9.7	48.8	9.2	39.7	1.1
M144	388.6	10.0	48.9	9.5	40.8	0.8

Within the flasher system we fully shade each cell of module M72 with an opaque cover and measure the module's $I(V)$ characteristics to determine the cells for the hot spot endurance test according to IEC 61215-2 MQT 09 [7]. Cells 1, 49, and 72 are the cells with the lowest shunt resistance and the cell 17 the cell with the highest shunt resistance. Subsequently, we determine the worst case shading conditions for these cell according to IEC 61215-2 MQT 09 [7].

For module M144 we only consider cell 1 of submodule M144-T and cell 73 submodule M144-B. Both cells are adjacent to the same bypass diode as illustrated in Fig 1 (b). We determine the worst case shading condition similarly to the cells in M72.

Figure 2: Photo of the steady state sun simulator with module M72 during the hot spot endurance test. In the photo cell 72 in the lower left corner is shaded with a cover.

2.3 Hot spot endurance test

Figure 2 shows a picture of module M72 in the steady-state sun simulator we employ for the hot spot endurance test according to IEC 61215-2 MQT 09 [7]. The halogen reflector lamps of the sun simulator illuminate the examined modules with an average irradiance intensity of 925 W m^{-2} . The illumination homogeneity is 3.5% measured with an UniformSun module [32]. The solar panel is mounted horizontally to the ground. A transparent temperature controlled plate between the module and the light source creates an artificial cool sky with a temperature of 23°C . During the test we measure the average module temperature of the unshaded cells with four thermocouples on the rear side of the module. An air condition maintains an ambient temperature of 22°C . The rear side of the module is cooled with an airflow to maintain a module temperature of $(50 \pm 10)^\circ\text{C}$. We measure an average wind speed of $(0.24 \pm 0.14) \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at the rear side with a hot wire anemometer. Further, we monitor the irradiance in the module plane with two pyranometers during the test.

Before shading the individual cells we measure the short circuit current of the module in the steady-state sun simulator employing a current clamp. We shade each cell in module M72 with the worst case shading fractions as determined according to the IEC standard [7]. During the test we measure the temperature with a Fluke Ti32 infrared camera [33]. For module M144 we start with shading only cell 1 of submodule M144-T and subsequently additionally shade cell 1 and cell 73 of submodule M144-B simultaneously.

After the test we re-measure the $I(V)$ characteristics of the modules. Furthermore, we measure the ultraviolet (UV) fluorescence of the module using our FLOIS system [34].

Figure 3: Reverse $I(V)$ characteristics of 6 PERC. The inset shows a reverse biased electroluminescence image of cell 1 at -24 V.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Breakdown characteristics of state-of-the-art PERC

Figure 3 shows the reverse $I(V)$ characteristics of six PERC cells. All cells show a homogeneous breakdown characteristic with a breakdown voltage below -20 V. The inset shows an electroluminescence image of cell 1 at -24 V indicating the local breakdown with red spots in the pattern of the Czochralski rings [35].

For the modeling of the breakdown characteristics we employ the model of Ruiz *et al.* [36,37]

$$I = \frac{I_{SC} - G_{sh}V - cV^2}{1 - \exp\left[B_e \left(1 - \sqrt{(\Phi_T - V_B)/(\Phi_T - V)}\right)\right]}. \quad (1)$$

Here G_{sh} is the shunt conductance, c is a parabolic term for the breakdown characteristics, B_e is a quasi constant parameter, Φ_T is the built-in junction potential, and V_B the breakdown voltage. In this work we consider a constant Φ_T of 0.850 V and that I_{SC} is 0 since we measured the reverse $I(V)$ characteristics in the dark. Table 1 summarizes the average parameters we extract from modeling our cell measurements with the double diode model in SCAN and the breakdown model.

We determine the temperature dependence of the breakdown voltage for all currents below -0.3 A to be

$$V_B(T) = -0.02T - 25.8, \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature. The negative temperature coefficient β of -0.02 V °C $^{-1}$ indicates

Table 2: $I(V)$ parameters of the cells, measured at 25 °C.

η [%]	I_{SC} [A]	V_{OC} [V]	FF [%]	I_{01} [pA]	I_{02} [nA]	G_{sh} [mS]	B_e -	C [fS V ⁻¹]	V_B [V]
21.3	9.6	665.5	81.5	57.6	269.7	3.0	5.0	22.2	-26.3

that the breakdown characteristic is a typical avalanche breakdown due to high local electric fields [38]. This is also visible in the inset of Fig. 3, where the red spots indicate the local breakdown. From the cell measurements we deduce that all PERC cells of the modules M72 and M144 have a similar breakdown down characteristics as depicted in Fig. 3. No cell shows a second breakdown as it may happen for c-Si solar cell [20]. Thus, we conclude that the cells heat up homogeneously in the hot spot endurance test and that the heat generation is evenly distributed over the cell surface.

3.2 Hot spot endurance test

Figure 5 shows the $I(V)$ characteristics for cell 1 of M72, when applying varying shading fractions S to the cell. The worst case condition is met, when the current of the shaded cell is equal to the I_{MPP} of the module before the bypass diode starts conducting. In Fig. 5 this is the case for a shading fraction S of 25 %. Similarly, we determine the shading fraction of the other cells. Table 3 lists the shading fraction for each cell we test in the hot spot endurance test.

Further, the table shows the peak temperature $T_{P,M}$ we measure during the hot spot endurance test with infrared camera. For the temperature evaluation we use a surface emissivity ϵ_s for the glass of 0.9 [39]. The uncertainty of the camera is ± 2 °C according to the manufacturer. The orientation of the camera differs for each cell from the normal of the module to avoid additional shading effects by the camera during the hot spot endurance test. Therefore, we also consider the directional emissivity to estimate the uncertainty of the temperature measurements [40, 41]. We determine the view angle of the camera for each cell and consider the values of Pantinakis *et al.* [40] as a worst case estimation. Table 3 lists the peak temperatures and the uncertainty we measure for the shaded cells in the modules M72 and M144.

Table 3: Worst case shading fraction S and measured peak temperature at the module surface $T_{P,M}$ for the cells we test in the hot spot endurance test.

Module	M72	M72	M72	M72	M144T	M144T
Cell	1	17	49	72	1	1&73
S [%]	25	19	25	22	25	25&32
$T_{P,M}$ [°C]	164±5	161±7	141±4	142±4	151±3	159±4

All examined cells heat up homogeneously and reach temperatures above 140 °C. Cell 1 in module M72 exhibits a peak temperature of 164 °C. This is a critical operating point for the module since at temperatures above 150 °C yellowing and embrittlement of the encapsulation material may occur [8, 16]. Temperatures above 180 °C may even lead to the de-soldering of the cell interconnection [42] or glass breakage [16]. Cells 49 and 72 are cooler than cells 1 and 17 in M72, which is due to the positioning of the cover. Cell 49 and 72 heat up homogeneously during the hot spot endurance test and thus, we position the cover in the center of the cell. For cell 1 and 17 one cell side appears cooler, with the cover positioned at the cell center. Therefore, we shift the cover to the cooler cell side according to IEC 61215 MQT 09 [7]. Note that the difference between both sides is only approximately 5 °C, without showing local hot spots.

For module M144 we position the cover at the cell edge, since for this case we observe higher temperatures for the cells in M72. We measure a 10 °C lower peak temperature for the half cell module, when shading only cell 1. Shading cells 1 and 73 simultaneously in module M144 we measure a peak temperature of (159 ± 4) °C. In this case both cells in the center of the module and the adjacent bypass diode (c.f. Fig. 1) generate heat. Due to the localized heat source this results in a similar peak temperature as for the full cell module M72.

Figure 4 shows the fluorescence image of module M72. Cells 1, 17, 49, and 72 appear brighter than the other cells of the module except in the areas where we apply the cover stripes to the cells

Figure 4: Fluorescence image of module M72 after the hot spot endurance test. During the hot spot test we shade cells 1, 17, 49, and 72.

during the hot spot endurance test. For cells 49 and 72 the cover is in the center and for cells 1 and 17 at the edge of the cell. Morlier *et al.* showed that heat induces the decomposition of the encapsulation polymer and the reaction products tend to fluoresce in the fluorescence image [34]. This fluorescence correlates with the yellowing of the encapsulation materials, which results in a reduction of the module power. Further, the degradation of the encapsulation material increases the risk of module failure [43].

All examined cells heat up homogeneously without showing local hot spots. Therefore we suggest the terminology of hot cells in case of mono crystalline solar cells instead of hot spots as it is typical for multi crystalline solar cells. Our results show that the risk of failure due to hot cells is larger for state-of-the-art modules with 72 full cells than for modules with half cells. Further, we measure significantly higher temperatures as reported for modules with less than 72 cell in the past [22]. This is due to the increasing module efficiency, higher current for each of the module's cells and the larger number of cells per string in the module. In comparison to the full cell module design, the half cell module design shows 10 °C lower peak temperatures when shading only one cell. However, shading two neighboring half cells from two parallel connected strings in a half cell module results in similar peak temperatures in terms of the measurement uncertainty as shading one full cell in a full cell module.

3.3 Electrical modeling

Modeling the $I(V)$ measurements of the module with varying cell shading We model the $I(V)$ characteristics of the modules with the double diode model and the breakdown model employing the values from table 2 as initial parameters. We assume ideality factors of 1 and 2 for the first and second diode, respectively. For the bypass diodes we consider a saturation current of 1 nA and an ideality factor of 1.

First, we model the $I(V)$ characteristics of the unshaded module M72 considering equal parameters for all 72 cells. For the modeling of the module's $I(V)$ characteristics the saturation current densities of the first and second diode as well as the shunt resistance are free fit parameters. Subsequently, we only reduce the I_{SC} of one cell by the shading fraction S to account for the shading of the cell in the flasher measurements. For the shading we consider an effective shading since internal reflections within the module and light impinging oblique to the normal of the module surface reduce the geometrical size of the cover. Our model fits best when reducing the geometrical shading by 3%.

Figure 5 shows the measured and the modeled $I(V)$ characteristics for cell 1 in M72 for a varying shading fraction S . The symbols indicate the measurement and the solid lines the modeling data. For a better illustration Fig. 5 only shows every 5th measurement value. The red dashed line (---) indicates the I_{MPP} of the unshaded module. The shading fraction S corresponds to the geometrical size of the opaque covers we apply to the cell in the flasher measurements. Table 4 lists the parameters we employ to model cell 1 in module M72.

Figure 5: $I(V)$ characteristics of the measured and simulated cell 1 of module M72. The red dashed line indicates the I_{MPP} of the unshaded module.

Table 4: Parameters for the electrical model of the solar modules.

I_{SC} [A]	I_{01} [pA]	I_{02} [pA]	G_{sh} [mS]	B_e -	C [fS V ⁻¹]	V_B [V]
9.7	34.8	258.3	7.4	5	22.2	-26.3

Our electrical model allows to determine the dissipated power in a partially shaded cell. For cell 1 in module M72 we simulate a dissipated power of 95 W. When shading more than one cell, the cells share the dissipated power, which results in lower temperatures during the hot spot endurance test.

Table 3 shows that this is not the case when shading two adjacent cells, each from another submodule in M144. In this case, both cells are reverse biased and generate heat. If the module operates at I_{SC} as it is required for the hot spot endurance test, the worst case shading condition is similar for both cell.

Modeling a half cell module in a PV system This worst case shading condition changes when considering a realistic scenario with an inverter holding the shaded module at the MPP of the unshaded modules in a PV system. Figure 6 shows the modeling results for three shading situations of module M144. The symbols indicate the operating point of each cell, which corresponds to the MPP of the PV system. In (a) we simulate the unshaded module, in (b) we shade cell 1 in submodule M144-T by 23 %, and in (c) we simultaneously shade cell 1 in submodule M144-T by 23 % and cell 73 in submodule M144-B by 5 %. Each graph in Fig. 6 shows the $I(V)$ characteristics of:

1. cell 1, representing a shaded cell in submodule M144-T with 23 % shading in Fig. 6 (b) and 6 (c).
2. Cell 12, an unshaded cell in the same string as cell 1 in submodule M144-T.
3. Cell 73, a shaded cell in submodule M144-B with 5 % shading in Fig. 6 (c).
4. Cell 84, an unshaded cell in the same string as cell 73 in submodule M144-B.
5. Cell 144 in submodule M144-B, a cell in an adjacent string without shaded cells. The $I(V)$ characteristic of this cell is equal to cell 74 of submodule M144-T.

Figure 6: Simulation of the half cell module with (a) no cell shaded, (b) cell 1 shaded by 23%, and (c) cell 1 shaded by 23% and cell 73 shaded 5%.

6. The $I(V)$ characteristic of the bypass diode that is parallel to the string with cell 1 and cell 73.

In Figure 6 (a) the module is unshaded and all cells are at the same operating point. Shading cell 1 by 23% in Fig. 6 (b) reduces the current of this cell. The inverter of the PV system holds all modules at the operating point, which is similar to the MPP of an unshaded module in case

of a large system with 20 modules. Due to the current limitation the operating point of cell 1 (\bullet) shifts in the negative voltage range and the cell dissipates 57 W. This cell also limits the current of all other cells in the string and thus, the operating point of cell 12 (\blacktriangle) shifts to a higher voltage to generate the same current as cell 1. Cell 144 (\blacklozenge) is still at the same operating point as in the unshaded module in Fig. 6 (a) and generating the same current. According to Kirchhoff’s law, the sum of the currents of the parallel strings holding cell 1 and cell 73 has to be identical to the sum of the parallel unshaded strings with cell 144 and 74. Hence, the operating point of cell 73 (\times) in submodule M144-B shifts to a lower voltage and the cell generates a higher current. This also applies to all cells in this string represented by cell 84 (\blacksquare) in Fig. 6 (b). Due to the shift to a lower voltage, cell 73 operates close to the short circuit operating point. Thus, only a small shading fraction of 5% is necessary to force cell 73 (\times) into reverse bias in Fig. 6 (c). Both cells dissipate power in Fig. 6 (c) with cell 1 dissipating 57 W and cell 73 dissipating 49 W.

Figure 1(a) shows that cell 1 and cell 73 are neighboring cells. In case both cells are shaded, e.g. by a leaf or bird droppings, both cells dissipate a power of 106 W, which results in similar heat generation as in a full cell module according to our measurements results in table 3. Further, only a mismatch of 5% is necessary for reverse biasing the second cell. Thus, production-related current mismatch of the individual cells and inhomogeneous front and rear side illuminations [44] can trigger this event. Nevertheless, the parallel connection of two sub-modules in the half cell module design reduces the risk for hotspots, since only the cells in the center of the module create such a local heat generation. In contrast, in a full cell module each cell may dissipate this power.

3.4 Thermal modeling of hot cells in a solar module

We perform 3 dimensional finite element modeling (FEM) employing Comsol Multiphysics to simulate the module temperature in the hot spot endurance test [45]. For the model we consider a 3×3 cell module. We simulate the cells embedded in-between two layers of ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) with a front side glass and a rear side backsheet. The rear side backsheet is either a glass for module M72 or a polymer backsheet for module M144. In the simulation we also account for the cell interconnection with five cell interconnection ribbons. The ribbons have a width of 1 mm and a thickness of 200 μm . Further, we consider the aluminum (Al) frame with a width of 1 cm.

In the thermal model we simulate steady-state conditions, i.e. the heat generation of a cell is in thermal equilibrium with the external environment due to conduction, convection and radiation [46]. For further details of the thermal model we refer to appendix 4. For the heat source of the unshaded cells we assume a power of 18 W, which results in a temperature of 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the module surface. This agrees with the measured average module temperature in the hot spot endurance test. For the unshaded parts of the partially shaded cell we use an additional heat source employing the dissipated power from our electrical model. Table 5 lists the individual material parameters we take from reference [47] and thicknesses of each component.

Table 5: Parameters for the thermal model

Component	thickness [mm]	k [W m $^{-1}$ K $^{-1}$]	ϵ_s
Glass	3	1.8	0.9
EVA	0.45	0.32	-
Silicon	0.18	149	-
Polymer Backsheet	0.3	0.56	0.9
Al frame	30	237	-

Figure 7 (a) shows a blended image of the thermal and the visual images of cell 1 measured during the hot spot endurance test. The peak temperature at the module surface is 164 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Figure 7 (b) shows the modeling of the same hot cell with a peak temperature of 166 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Our thermal model allows to qualitatively remodel the experimental results within the measurement uncertainty of the peak temperature.

(a) Measurement

(b) Simulation

Figure 7: Temperature distribution of cell 12 in the hot spot endurance test, when shading the cell with a 4 cm wide cover stripe.

3.5 Temperature prediction for future cells and modules

We employ our electrical and thermal model to simulate the module peak temperature in seven scenarios for future cell and module developments. As initial input parameters we employ the $I(V)$ characteristics of M144. For the electrical model we consider a constant shading fraction and a module temperature of 55°C in each scenario. All scenarios consider a half cell module design with three bypass diodes in the center and a shading ratio S of 25% as in our experiment. In this study we consider the following scenarios:

- i) Verification of the experimental results with the half cell module M144.
- ii) Increasing the irradiance of 925 W m^{-2} as in our experiments to 1000 W m^{-2} .
- iii) Improvement of the PERC cell efficiency of 0.5% within the next two years [24].
- iv) Increasing wafer format [19], which results for M4 in a half cell area of 129.1 cm^2 and
- v) for M6 in a half cell area of 137.1 cm^2 .

- vi) For M12 wafer formats we consider 10 half cells per string
- vii) and 15 cells per string, with 1/3 of the full cell area.

Table 6 summarizes our simulation results for the scenarios.

Table 6: Parameters as well as surface temperature of cells and module for the simulated scenarios.

Scenario	Wafer format	Cell area [cm ²]	cells per string/module	η_{cell}	P_{MPP} [W _P]	P_{diss} [W]	$T_{\text{P,C}}$ [°C]	$T_{\text{P,M}}$ [°C]
i)	-	124.9	12/144	21.6	388.6	52	159	152
ii)	-	124.9	12/144	21.6	388.6	56	168	160
iii)	-	124.9	12/144	22.1	397.4	58	171	163
iv)	M4	129.1	12/144	22.1	410.8	60	171	163
v)	M6	137.1	12/144	22.1	436.1	64	173	165
vi)	M12	220.5	10/100	22.1	487.0	82	158	151
vii)	M12	147.0	15/150	22.1	487.1	86	186	176

We start in scenario i) with remodeling the experimental results of the hot spot endurance test of M144. The simulated module has a power P_{MPP} of 388.6 W_P under STC and the cell efficiency inside the module η_{cell} is 21.6%. The power dissipation of the shaded cell is 52 W. For this case our FEM simulation results in a module peak temperature $T_{\text{P,M}}$ of 152 °C, which is within the measurement uncertainty of our experiment (c.f. table 3). The FEM simulation also allows to determine the peak temperature at the hot cell surface $T_{\text{P,C}}$, which is 159 °C in scenario i). Increasing the illumination intensity from 925 W m⁻² to 1000 W m⁻² increases $T_{\text{P,M}}$ to 160 °C. In scenario iii) we assume that current and voltage contribute equally to improve the efficiency by 0.5%, which increases the module’s peak temperature at the surface to 163 °C. An increasing wafer format up-to M6 wafers in scenario v) results in a $T_{\text{P,M}}$ of 165 °C in the hot spot endurance test. This temperature is similar to the temperature in the hot spot endurance test for the full cell module M72. Thus, employing the M6 wafer format for half cells in a module with 144 cells and three bypass diodes can result in critical temperatures for the encapsulation material under inhomogeneous module illumination.

For further increasing wafer sizes we consider less cells per string in scenario vi) or reducing the cell area by 1/3 in scenario vii). Both scenarios result in a similar module power of 487 W_P. However, using 15 cells per string increases the reverse biasing of the shaded cell and results in a power dissipation of 86 W. This results in the highest module peak temperature of 176 °C in our simulations. The module with M12 half cells in scenario vi) exhibits a lower module peak temperature according to our simulation. However, the module’s I_{SC} of 17.8 A is challenging for the bypass diodes. In case of a fully shaded cell the bypass diode has to conduct the current of the unshaded cells, which significantly increases the power dissipation in the diode for 17.8 A in scenario vi) compared to 11.8 A in scenario vii).

4 Conclusion

We examine the reverse characteristics of state-of-the-art c-Si PERC cells. All cells in this study show a homogeneous breakdown characteristics in reverse $I(V)$ and electroluminescence measurements. This is also evident in the hot spot endurance test of two full-sized modules, one featuring 72 full cells and the other featuring 144 half cells. During the hot spot endurance test the heat generation is evenly distributed over the cells. Thus, we introduce the terminology of hot cells. Applying the worst case shading to the c-Si cells, the cover should be positioned such that the illuminated contiguous area is maximal.

Our experiments show that market available high efficiency solar modules with 72 full cells reach temperatures of 164 °C. This is a critical temperature since the lamination material and the backsheets are typically designed for maximum permanent temperatures of 150 °C. Our UV fluorescence images reveal that maintaining the test conditions for 1 h already damages the module’s encapsulation polymer. Accumulated over the lifetime of a PV module this reduces the module’s power output and increases the risk of a module failure. Temperatures of 170 °C may lead to bubbles and deformation of the backsheets material, or even to a detachment of

the junction box [16]. Furthermore, the hot cell temperature should not raise above the solder temperature. The liquidus temperature of Sn63Pb37 solder is at 183 °C and for lead free solders around 220 °C. Above this temperature leaching of the silver contact may occur [42], resulting in solder joint failures. Temperatures close to the solidus intermetallic phase can also weaken the solder joint [48]. The hot cells may also increase the risk of glass breakage due to temperature gradients in the glass of future modules.

We develop an electrical and a thermal model that reproduces our experimental results. The electrical model allows to show that for half cell modules operating at MPP in a PV system, the worst case shading of one cell in a submodule results in a shift to lower voltages of the cells in the parallel connected, unshaded submodule. Thus, shading a cell in the parallel connected submodule only by a small fraction forces the cell into reverse bias. This makes the unshaded submodule sensitive for hot cells due to production-related current mismatch and inhomogeneous front and rear side illumination in case of bifacial modules [44]. Our results agree with the findings of Qian *et al.* [22]. In addition to their work, we also show that this effect can result in critical heat generation of the cells in the center of the half cell module. Our experiment results in a 8 °C higher module peak temperature when shading two cells in the center of the module compared to a single shaded cell. This can be decisive for high-performance modules that operate at temperatures close to the heat tolerance limit of the encapsulation material under inhomogeneous illumination.

The thermal model shows that half cell modules are advantageous compared to full cell modules. Employing the electrical parameters of the full cell module in a module with half cells results in a peak temperature of 145 °C in our simulation, which is 20 °C cooler than the peak temperature of the full cell module. Also in the experiment the half cell module is cooler, although it has a 21 W higher module power output than the full cell module. Half cells are thus advantageous due to the larger perimeter to area aspect ratio. Similarly, the increasing wafer format affects this aspect ratio, which results in higher module temperatures for modules employing cells with larger wafer formats. Furthermore, the parallel connection of the two submodules reduces the current mismatch due to inhomogeneous ground albedo.

Our results show, that the three bypass diodes per module architecture needs to be redesigned for high efficiency modules with cells of M6 wafer format and 72 cells. Considering that we test the modules only according to the IEC standard, particularly the higher current of bifacial modules will result in even higher module temperatures in case of current mismatch. Thus, also the IEC61215-2 MQT 09 standard for the hot spot endurance test needs to be adjusted for bifacial half cell modules.

A solution to address the hot cell issue is to employ less cells per bypass diode and place the diodes at the long edge of the module as proposed by Qian *et al.* [49]. Employing power electronics to operate each cell string at the individual MPP [50] or at open circuit offers another possibility to mitigate hot cells [51].

□

A. Thermal model

In the thermal model we simulate steady-state conditions, i.e. the heat generation of a cell q_{cell} is in thermal equilibrium with the external environment due to conduction, convection and radiation [46]

$$q_{\text{cell}} = -k\nabla^2 T + q_{\text{rad}} + q_{\text{con}}, \quad (3)$$

where k is the thermal conductivity, T is the temperature, and q_{rad} and q_{con} are the heat flux by radiation and convection. The radiation heat flux q_{rad} is given by

$$q_{\text{rad}} = \epsilon_s \sigma (T^4 - T_s^4), \quad (4)$$

where T_s is the temperature of the surrounding surfaces, σ the Stefan Boltzman constant, and ϵ_s the surface emissivity of the glass and backsheet, respectively. For T_s we consider the temperature of the artificial sky T_{sky} for the front side and the ambient temperature T_{amb} for the rear side of the module as determined in our experiments.

For the convection term we have

$$q_{\text{con}} = h (T - T_{\text{amb}}). \quad (5)$$

We consider natural convection at the front side with a heat transfer coefficient

$$h_{\text{natural}} = \frac{k}{L} 0.15 Ra^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (6)$$

and a laminar forced convection flow on the rear side

$$h_{\text{force}} = 2 \frac{k}{L} \frac{0.3387 Pr^{\frac{1}{3}} Re^{\frac{1}{2}}}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{0.0468}{Pr}\right)\right]^{\frac{1}{4}}}. \quad (7)$$

Here L is the area over perimeter ratio of the module, k is the thermal conductivity, Pr is Prandelt's number, Re is Reynold's number, and Ra Rayleigh's number.

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